

DARK SPOTS ON THE SURFACE OF MARS MAY BE HOLES IN THE CEILING OF ICE CAVES.

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Abstract

In the early 2000s, 7 dark spots were found on the slopes of the Arsya volcano. Studies have shown that they are sinkholes in the ceiling to large volcanic caves. In the Hebrus Valles, near the Elysium volcanic region, many channels with a width of several hundred meters to several kilometers have been found. At the end of the canals there is an elongated pit with dimensions of 1800 × 1125 m and a depth of up to 500 m. The bottom and slopes of the pit are covered with sediments and boulders up to several meters in diameter. Such pits can hold water ice under the surface. Studies of images of the surface of Mars at the Pavonis Mons volcano, obtained with the "THEMIS" camera from the "Mars Odyssey" spacecraft, allowed the discovery of many cave tubes. They are visible as chains of collapses with a flat base and sloping sides. There are also several dark pitfalls to caves. In Acidalia Planitia, they found glacial streams and ravines that resemble rivers on Earth. They are shallow and located on gentle slopes of elevations facing the equator. Their orientation relative to the equator indicates the need to take into account the control of insolation. The formation of pits can be caused by the cooling of the lava and the subsidence of the surface layers due to the melting of the ice.

Keywords: Mars, dark sinkholes, glacial caves, volcanic caves, landslides.

Many mountain ranges and flat areas with volcanic and impact craters of various ages have been found on the surface of Mars [14-16, 19]. In the early 2000s, 7 dark spots were found on the slopes of the Arsya volcano. They were given the female names of Wendy, Dana, Jeanne, Abby, Annie, Nikki and Chloe. Later studies showed that these dark spots are actually deep depressions in the ceiling of very large volcanic caves. They could be formed as a result of surface material sinking into underground cavities. Since they form chains and faults, with a distinct pattern, they are most likely caused by surface stretching. Volcanic processes could be the cause of stretching and cracking [28]. Rocks from the surface could later fall into these cavities, leaving depressions there [21, 27].

Tyrrhenus Mons is one of the oldest volcanoes on Mars. Therefore, many radially located ravines formed on its slopes (Fig. 1, left). During volcanic eruptions, lava penetrated through the frozen layers of the soil and flowed down the slopes. Unlike most other Martian volcanoes [20], its slopes consist mainly of layers of volcanic ash rather than basaltic material. Such a difference led to the fact that the slopes of the volcano were easily eroded, forming wide channels in different places from several craters on its top.

Glacier caves are also formed in the body of glaciers under the influence of melt water. They form passages up to several meters high, several hundred meters long, and 100 m deep or more. Billions of years ago, there were huge oceans, seas, long river systems and lakes on the surface of Mars. At that time, Mars was supposed to be similar to Earth [2]. But since then, this planet has been deprived of both an atmosphere [17] and liquid water [25]. It is even possible that certain forms of life could develop on Mars [5, 11-13]. However, no proof of this has yet been found.

The "Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter" probes the surface of the planet from orbit [6, 7], obtaining many high-quality images of the surface. In the Hebrus Valles, adjacent to the Elysium volcanic region, there are also numerous channels with a width of several hundred meters to several kilometers. In the place where one of the channels ends, there is an elongated pit (Fig. 1, right) approximately 1800 m long and 1125 m wide. Based on the shadow cast by the wall on the bottom of the pit, the depth of the pit was estimated at 500 m. The bottom of the pit is covered with sediments and a layer of boulders. The slopes of the pit are also strewn with boulders up to several meters in diameter.

*Figure 1. Left – Tyrrhenus Mons obtained by «Mars Odyssey» 24.2.2022
(https://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/figures/PIA25159_fig1.png).*

Right – pit is believed to be approximately 1875 × 1125 m (NASA/JPL-Caltech/UA Arizona).

Such pits can hold water ice under the surface [10], which could be used by future long-term settlements [24, 26]. But in addition to providing water, pits can also be used as a natural shelter for settlements. Therefore, they are potential landing sites for human exploration.

The round black spot in the "THEMIS" image is also a hole in the roof (Fig. 2), possibly a Martian lava tube or glacial cave. Studies of more than two hundred high-resolution images of the Pavonis Mons region of Mars, obtained by the "THEMIS" camera from the "Mars Odyssey" spacecraft, have revealed many Martian lava tubes. They are visible as chains of collapses

with a flat base and sloping sides. But several dark vertical dips were also found there. These holes were anomalous compared to normal chain pit craters. They resembled a relatively straight hole going down to the surface.

It has been suggested that they are light "windows" when a small part of the roof of the cave collapsed. They were colder than the surface during the day, and warmer than it at night. This was to be expected. After all, temperatures on the surface of Mars have a significant diurnal range of changes, while temperatures below the surface remain almost unchanged. According to estimates, the dimensions of the hole turned out to be approximately, 190 × 160 m and 115 m in depth.

Figure 2. A possible hole in the roof of a Martian lava tube (https://www.redshift-live.com/binaries/asset/image/28604/image/Martian_Hole.jpg).

Mars is the most Earth-like planet in the solar system. It contains numerous landscapes and landforms that show similarities to known features on Earth. Particularly striking examples are the Martian glacial streams and ravines that resemble their river-cut terrestrial counterparts. They are the ones that have been intensively studied over the past few decades. This allows us to understand the evolution of the Martian surface. One of these features is called pits [4] (Fig. 3).

Pits of this type are found mainly in the southern part of Acidalia Planitia on Mars, west and northwest of Cydonia Mensae (Fig. 4, Left). Until recently, it was believed that most oval depressions on terrestrial planets and satellites are impact craters [23]. However, after obtaining increasingly high-resolution images of the surface of Mars, researchers began to see details that cast doubt on their interpretation of the result of a meteorite impact. These pits in the form of chains look like a sunken surface. Each of them has a rounded, elongated, or irregular shape with raised edges and reaches several hundred meters in diameter.

Figure 3. Different morphological variants of pits located in Acidalia Planitia. A) Almost circular pits with many boulders around the edges (HiRISE ID: ESP_019783_2115_RED). B) Several elongate pits without obvious overlying marginal deposits (HiRISE ID: ESP_026521_2130_RED). C) A cluster of several pits on the slope of a topographic object directed to the equator (HiRISE ID: ESP_026521_2130_RED).

They are mainly located on gentle (up to 2°) slopes of elevations facing the equator, on the inner walls of craters, etc. Usually they form chains, but they also exist separately [31]. The lack of overlapping pit ridges indicates that most of them were formed more or less simultaneously (Fig. 4, right). Although sometimes smaller pits can be nested in larger ones. This indicates the possibility of numerous pit formation episodes.

The pits appear to be relatively shallow and the raised edges consist of boulders. The bottom of some pits is partially covered by eolian formations, and there is no evidence of fluvial activity. Their occurrence does not coincide with the latitude-dependent deposits of ice and dust, which cover large bands in the middle latitudes.

Figure 4. Left – map of the great northern plains of Acidalia Planitia. The light circle shows the location of most documented pits. Right – a chain of pits located on the equator-facing slope of a local ridge. The pits appear young based on the well-preserved rims. Some pits show limited eolian deposition and ripple forms (NASA/JPL/UoA for HiRISE ID: PSP_PSP_008641_2105_RED)

Before the appearance of the images obtained by "HiRISE", it was believed that pits were formed similarly to terrestrial aeolian emissions [2, 3, 22]. But the irregular shape of many pits contradicts the formation of secondary craters or volcanic features. Instead, their orientation relative to the equator suggests the need to account for insolation control. In addition, the slightly raised side walls of all pits may indicate high-energy excavation by some unknown agent. One of the possibilities is the action of gas jets created by sublimation of CO₂ under deposits of dry ice. However, thick slabs of dry ice are unlikely to be present at the low latitudes of Mars, where these pits are observed.

Another possibility for the formation of pits is that they are residual landforms from the times when the dust- and ice-rich upper shell part of the surface spread further to the equator, or when insolation-controlled water discharges occurred on the slopes [9, 29]. However, the choice between these possibilities has not yet been made. It can also be assumed that the formation of pits can be caused by cryogenic processes in frozen soils [18].

Such explanations are suggested by images obtained by the "HiRISE" camera with a resolution of up to 0.3 m per pixel. Similar cavities are found on the slopes of Martian craters on Arsia Mons, Pavonis Mons in the Northern Hemisphere, and Alba Patera in the Southern Hemisphere. Such cavities can be compared with volcanic caves of the Hawaiian type. There you can also see linear crater formations, very similar to the craters on the volcanoes of Mars. Based on the ice capacity map obtained by the "Mars Odyssey" spacecraft, a very small amount of water ice is observed in these places on the volcanic slopes: up to 2-4% by hydrogen content. Therefore, the sinkholes found there cannot be explained only by the thawing of the ice under the surface.

The maximum volcanic activity on Mars occurred approximately 3.6 billion years ago. And it almost ended, probably about 1.8 billion years ago. The chains of depressions on Arsia Mons fit into these volcanic processes. And a number of chain depressions in the central part of Chryse Planitia with coordinates 30.36°N and 323.37°E (Fig. 2) are most likely caused by the collapse and subsidence of the surface layers. This mechanism may be responsible for the formation of a series of collapsed canyons, or elongated forms of land subsidence, as a result of melting ice below the surface.

Such forms are most likely related to ice melting systems [1] caused by the auxiliary topography of the area, or even to tectonics and internal cracks in some rocks. Then, flowing water or brine below the surface, coming from the ice sheet, could accumulate during freezing and create a longitudinal hill; later it could collapse due to seasonal [8] thawing, forming ravines and canyons.

At the ends of these ravines, you can sometimes see the residual traces of a leak, as if a crack had appeared in the soil through which the liquid leaked to the surface. That is, the melting of ice can create such a depression; sometimes it will be slightly winding and with

gentle slopes. On Earth, these phenomena are observed in Canada and Alaska.

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